

The Role of Statin in Stroke Management

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Abstract:

Background: Stroke is an important cause of disability and death globally. Statins, primarily used to lower cholesterol, have demonstrated potential in reducing stroke incidence and recurrence. This study evaluates the effectiveness of statins in preventing stroke and managing stroke recurrence in high-risk individuals.

Methods: A prospective study was conducted at Darbhanga Medical College over one year with 100 patients, either at high risk of stroke or with a history of stroke or transient ischemic attack (TIA). Patients received statins, and their cholesterol levels, incidence of stroke recurrence, and any adverse effects were monitored and analyzed.

Results: Statin therapy significantly lowered total and LDL cholesterol levels from baseline, with total cholesterol reduced from 240 mg/dL to 185 mg/dL and LDL from 160 mg/dL to 105 mg/dL by the end of the study. Stroke recurrence was observed in only 8% of patients, while 92% remained stroke-free. Adverse effects, primarily muscle pain (15%) and liver abnormalities (5%), were minimal and manageable.

Conclusion: Statins proved effective in reducing cholesterol and stroke recurrence, with a favorable risk-benefit profile. These findings favour the continued use of statins in high-risk stroke patients, highlighting the need for personalized dosages to balance efficacy and side effects.

Keywords: Stroke, Statins, Cholesterol, Secondary Prevention.

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Introduction

Statins are crucial for the management and prevention of stroke, especially in individuals with a high risk of cardiovascular diseases [1]. Originally designed to decrease cholesterol levels, statins have been found to be effective in reducing the risk of ischemic strokes by stabilizing plaques in the arteries, decreasing inflammation, and improving blood vessel function. Their primary action is the inhibition of HMG-CoA reductase, an enzyme critical in cholesterol production. High cholesterol levels contribute to plaque formation in the arteries, causing atherosclerosis and an increased risk of strokes [2,3].

In stroke management, statins are used not only as preventive medication but also as part of secondary prevention strategies for patients who have already experienced a stroke or transient ischemic attack (TIA) [4]. Studies have shown that individuals on statin therapy have lower chances of recurrent strokes and improved long-term outcomes, partly due to statins' anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects. Moreover, they benefit brain health by enhancing blood flow and protecting against further vascular damage [5,6].

However, the use of statins in stroke management is not without consideration. Potential side effects, such as muscle pain and liver function

abnormalities, must be balanced against their benefits, especially in elderly or complex cases [7]. Nonetheless, for many patients, statins remain an essential part of stroke management, contributing significantly to both primary and secondary prevention and ultimately improving quality of life and survival rates [8,9].

The study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of statins in decreasing the incidence and recurrence of strokes, as well as to assess their effect on overall outcomes in stroke patients. Additionally, the study seeks to identify potential benefits and risks associated with statin use in stroke management.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This prospective study was conducted at Darbhanga Medical College over one year, involving 100 patients who either had a history of stroke or were identified as high-risk for stroke. The study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of statins in decreasing stroke incidence and recurrence, as well as assess any associated risks and benefits.

Study Population

- **Number of Patients:** 100

- **Inclusion Criteria:** Patients with a history of stroke or transient ischemic attack (TIA) and those at high risk of stroke.
- **Exclusion Criteria:** Patients with contraindications to statins or significant liver disease were excluded from the study.

Intervention: Patients received statin therapy with dosages tailored to their individual cholesterol levels and clinical risk profiles. Standardized guidelines were followed to adjust dosages as needed over the study period, ensuring optimal cholesterol management in each patient.

Data Collection: Regular follow-ups were scheduled throughout the year to monitor patients' progress. Key data points collected during follow-ups included:

- **Cholesterol Levels:** Lipid profiles were regularly measured to assess the effectiveness of statin therapy.

- **Stroke Events:** Any occurrence of new or recurrent strokes was recorded and analyzed.
- **Adverse Effects:** Patients were monitored for potential side effects of statins, such as muscle pain or liver function abnormalities.

Outcome Measures: The primary outcomes of the study were the reduction in the incidence and recurrence of strokes among participants. Secondary outcomes included improvements in cholesterol levels, monitoring of potential side effects, and overall patient outcomes related to stroke risk management.

Data Analysis: Data collected were statistically analyzed to determine the effectiveness of statins in stroke prevention and to evaluate the balance of benefits and risks.

Results

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Patients

Characteristic	Value
Total Patients	100
Age (mean $\pm$ SD)	65 $\pm$ 10 years
Male	60 (60%)
Female	40 (40%)
History of Stroke/TIA	70 (70%)
High-Risk, No Prior Stroke	30 (30%)
Average Baseline Cholesterol Level (mg/dL)	240 $\pm$ 30

This table shows the baseline characteristics of the 100 patients included in the study. The majority were over the age of 65, and 70% had a past history of stroke or TIA, while 30% were high-risk individuals with no previous stroke. The average baseline cholesterol level was 240 mg/dL.

Table 2: Effect of Statin Therapy on Cholesterol Levels

Measurement	Baseline (mg/dL)	After 6 Months (mg/dL)	After 1 Year (mg/dL)
Total Cholesterol	240 $\pm$ 30	200 $\pm$ 25	185 $\pm$ 20
LDL Cholesterol	160 $\pm$ 20	120 $\pm$ 15	105 $\pm$ 12
HDL Cholesterol	40 $\pm$ 10	42 $\pm$ 9	45 $\pm$ 8
Triglycerides	180 $\pm$ 35	150 $\pm$ 30	140 $\pm$ 28

This table displays the changes in lipid profiles over the study period. Statin therapy significantly decreased total cholesterol and LDL cholesterol levels from baseline to the 6-month and 1-year follow-ups. HDL cholesterol showed a slight increase, indicating improved cardiovascular health. Triglycerides also decreased, supporting the role of statins in cholesterol management.

Table 3: Stroke Incidence and Adverse Effects During Study

Outcome	Number of Patients (%)
Recurrent Stroke	8 (8%)
No Stroke Recurrence	92 (92%)
Muscle Pain	15 (15%)
Liver Function Abnormalities	5 (5%)

This table summarizes stroke recurrence and adverse effects observed during the study. Among the 100 patients, 8% experienced a recurrent stroke, while 92% remained stroke-free. Common adverse effects included muscle pain (15%) and liver

function abnormalities (5%), which were monitored throughout the study.

Discussion

The study conducted at Darbhanga Medical College provides strong evidence supporting the role of

statins in stroke prevention and management among high-risk individuals and those with a history of stroke or transient ischemic attack (TIA). Over one year, statin therapy significantly reduced cholesterol levels, particularly LDL cholesterol, which is strongly associated with cardiovascular and cerebrovascular health. The reduction in recurrent stroke rates (8%) aligns with current literature suggesting that statins are effective in secondary stroke prevention, corroborating previous studies that emphasize statin benefits for individuals with atherosclerotic disease (Amarencu et al., 2016) [10].

A similar study by Amarencu et al. (2016) showed that high-dose statin therapy significantly decreased the risk of ischemic stroke recurrence. Additionally, a meta-analysis by Collins et al. (2017) [11] showed that statins can reduce stroke risk by approximately 25% for every 1 mmol/L reduction in LDL cholesterol. These findings are consistent with the outcomes observed in this study, where cholesterol levels were significantly lowered, contributing to a marked reduction in recurrent strokes.

Despite these positive outcomes, some adverse effects, particularly muscle pain (15%) and liver abnormalities (5%), were observed, which aligns with reported side effects in other studies. For example, the STAREE trial (Harrison et al., 2020) [12] noted that muscle pain was one of the most commonly reported side effects, especially among older adults. Careful patient selection and monitoring are thus critical to balancing the benefits and potential risks of statin therapy.

Future Aspects of the Study

The findings from this study point to several potential areas for future research:

1. **Long-term Effects:** Further studies with a longer follow-up period would be valuable to assess the sustained impact of statins on stroke prevention and overall survival.
2. **Dose Optimization:** Exploring the effectiveness of different statin dosages in minimizing adverse effects while maximizing stroke prevention outcomes could improve patient adherence and outcomes.
3. **Biomarkers for Risk Assessment:** Future studies could investigate biomarkers or genetic factors to identify individuals who would benefit most from statin therapy while minimizing adverse reactions.
4. **Combination Therapies:** Examining the potential benefits of combining statins with other cardiovascular drugs or lifestyle interventions could further reduce stroke risk and improve patient outcomes [13-15].

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that statin therapy is effective in reducing cholesterol levels, thereby lowering the risk of recurrent stroke in patients at high risk or with a prior history of stroke/TIA. The observed reduction in LDL cholesterol and improved lipid profiles reinforce the cardiovascular and cerebrovascular benefits of statins. While side effects were noted, the overall risk-benefit profile favors the use of statins in this population. These results contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting statins as a cornerstone in stroke management and highlight the need for personalized treatment approaches to optimize both efficacy and tolerability.

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